

**FEMININE POWER ‘LOST’ AND FEMININE POWER ‘REGAINED’:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TALBOT DONALDSON’S (1966),
SEAMUS HEANEY’S (1999) AND MARIA DAHVANA HEADLEY’S (2018)
TRANSLATIONS OF BEOWULF**

Volha KORBUT SALMAN, Associate Professor, PhD
(Yozgat Bozok University, Republic of Türkiye)

volha.k.salman@bozok.edu.tr

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8808-2594>

Received: May 24, 2025 | Reviewed: June 2, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

Translations of “Beowulf” often obscure the role of women in Anglo-Saxon society: formal equivalence translators, such as Talbot Donaldson (1966), replicate the text literally, but lack clarity, while dynamic equivalence translators, such as Seamus Heaney (1999), prioritize modern readability over accuracy. Both approaches diminish female authority and often reduce women to mead-bearers and mourners. Maria Dahvana Headley (2018), in her turn, breaks tradition with her subversive transcreation of “Beowulf” in the novel “The Mere Wife”, which centers on female characters. This paper compares translations of “Beowulf” by Donaldson, Heaney, and Headley, so as to reclaim the female power present in the original Old English epic but lost in subsequent patriarchal renditions.